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2025

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL SPORTS WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION FOR SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Abstract: The establishment of a healthy lifestyle (HL) in primary school students is facilitated by a series of pedagogical methods and techniques that form an integral component of harmonious personality development. This educational process is interconnected with the moral, aesthetic, and intellectual growth of the child. The integration of national sports and traditional games into the educational environment aims to cultivate a well-rounded personality characterized by physical health, spiritual and aesthetic maturity, cultural and historical competence, and the ability to sustain healthy lifestyle principles. Research shows that children of primary school age demonstrate high sensitivity to the pedagogical influence of ethno-cultural creativity, folk games, and sports. This sensitivity contributes both to the assimilation of cultural models and the enrichment of practical skills. Within the framework of ongoing projects promoting healthy lifestyles among this age group, the following methodologies are applied: structured daily routines, rational nutrition practices, and the inclusion of ethno-sport activities and game-based exercises to enhance motor abilities and overall health.

Key words: Physical education, sports, schoolchildren, national games, game-based activities.

Annotatsiya: Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari orasida sog'lom turmush tarzini shakllantirish turli pedagogik usullar va metodlar orqali amalga oshiriladi. Ular shaxsning har tomonlama uyg'un rivojlanishi jarayonining ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi. Mazkur ta'limiy jarayon bolaning ma'naviy, estetik va intellektual o'sishi bilan uzviy bog'liqdir. Milliy sport turlari va xalq o'yinlarini ta'lim muhitiga integratsiya qilishdan maqsad – jismonan sog'lom, ma'naviy yetuk, estetik didli, tarixiy va madaniy kompetensiyaga ega bo'lgan hamda sog'lom turmush tarzini barqaror shakllantirish qobiliyatiga ega shaxsni tarbiyalashdir. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari etno-madaniy ijodkorlik, xalq o'yinlari va sport vositalarining pedagogik ta'siriga sezgir bo'lib, bu holat nafaqat madaniy qadriyatlarni o'zlashtirishga, balki amaliy ko'nikmalarni boyitishga ham xizmat qiladi. Sog'lom turmush tarzini shakllantirish bo'yicha olib borilayotgan loyihalar doirasida quyidagi metodologiyalar qo'llanilmoqda: kun tartibini tizimli tashkil etish, oqilona ovqatlanish madaniyatini shakllantirish hamda milliy sport mashqlari va o'yin faoliyatini joriy etish orqali bolalarning jismoniy qobiliyatlari va umumiy sog'lig'ini mustahkamlash.

Kalit so'zlar: Jismoniy tarbiya, sport, o'quvchilar, milliy o'yinlar, o'yin faoliyati.

Аннотация: Формирование здорового образа жизни (ЗОЖ) у учащихся начальных классов обеспечивается системой педагогических методов и приёмов, которые являются неотъемлемой частью гармоничного развития личности. Этот образовательный процесс тесно связан с нравственным, эстетическим и интеллектуальным становлением ребёнка. Интеграция национальных видов спорта и народных игр в образовательную среду направлена на воспитание всесторонне развитой личности, характеризующейся физическим здоровьем, духовной и эстетической зрелостью, культурно-исторической компетентностью, а также способностью формировать устойчивые принципы здорового образа жизни. Исследования показывают, что дети младшего школьного возраста проявляют высокую чувствительность к педагогическому влиянию этнокультурного творчества, народных игр и спорта. Эта восприимчивость способствует не только усвоению культурных образцов, но и обогащению практических навыков. В рамках действующих проектов по формированию ЗОЖ применяются следующие методики: структурированный режим дня, формирование культуры рационального питания, а также включение этноспортивных упражнений и игровых занятий для развития двигательных способностей и укрепления здоровья.

Ключевые слова: Физическое воспитание, спорт, школьники, национальные игры, игровые виды деятельности.

INTRODUCTION

It is vital that physical education and sport are given due consideration as fundamental components of the educational and upbringing process for younger schoolchildren. The issue of education has deep historical roots, and its modern forms are determined by specific social conditions, being the product of a long spiritual and moral evolution of mankind. The integration of scientific research in the domain of physical culture and sport in the social and national context is of paramount importance, a notion reflected in the work of the World Congress "Sport in Modern Society" and the forum "Olympic Sport and Sport for All", which are aimed at consolidating society. The systematic organisation of national games and sporting events in various countries is driven by the objective of promoting and developing healthy lifestyles among children, adolescents, and adults.

The diversity of targeted national sports disciplines, in conjunction with the principle of unity within the framework of the state's updated physical culture and sports system, which is characterised by an ethnocultural and humanistic orientation, signifies a promising direction and is being utilised in educational activities with children. The key characteristics of these movements include a focus on mass participation and the targeted development of historically established national and international traditions integrated into the lives of the younger generation. This process is organically linked to the national idea, which is why the relevant practice has spread to various countries and has become established as a routine activity of international institutions. The objective of this initiative is to cultivate a sense of patriotism among schoolchildren through the incorporation of dedicated courses within the curriculum, the designation of specific class periods for these courses, their integration within physical education lessons, and the organisation of pertinent school-based events.

In the context of the integration of national and international traditions, physical education and sport have been identified as a means of fostering the development of not only physically robust but also spiritually mature personalities, as well as promoting a healthy lifestyle among young people from preschool to primary school age. Pedagogical activities in the domain of physical education and sport exert a dual influence on the development of children's mental qualities in real-world scenarios that are frequently characterised by instability. Empirical evidence demonstrates that engagement in national sports is conducive to the adoption of a healthy lifestyle and enhances physical health among primary school children, a development that is of significant importance both for the individual and for society as a whole. The sports education system exerts a profound influence on personal characteristics, encompassing moral and intellectual domains, cognitive and communication skills, as well as health culture. This influences the formation of value orientations that are pivotal for both the individual well-being of the child and public health.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of forming a healthy lifestyle among schoolchildren has been widely discussed in pedagogical and medical sciences. Doroshkevich, Nashkevich, and Murav'eva in their work *Osnovy valeologii i shkol'noy gigieny* emphasize that health education in schools requires systematic pedagogical approaches that integrate physical development with hygiene culture. Similarly, Kochashkin in *Metodika fizicheskogo vospitaniya* highlights the role of structured physical education in shaping both physical endurance and moral qualities of children, underlining that early school age is a critical stage for health culture formation.

Contemporary studies also reflect on the integration of physical culture with modern pedagogical demands. Lubisheva in *Sportizatsiya v obsheobrazovatel'noy shkole* stresses the necessity of mass participation in sports to ensure not only physical development but also socialisation of children. Luk'yanenko in his textbook *Fizicheskaya kul'tura: osnovy znaniy* presents the theoretical basis of physical education, linking it with value orientations that influence both individual and collective well-being. These works collectively demonstrate that national sports and traditional games, when introduced in the curriculum, enrich children's personal growth and social competence.

More recent contributions provide evidence on specific challenges and innovations. Kengesbayevich in *Didactics of Physical Culture and Sport (2025)* and his research on *Readiness of Social Pedagogues to Work with Children with Disabilities (2024)* reveal how adaptive and inclusive approaches in physical education can foster resilience and psychological well-being. Peshkova and Peshkov (2012) argue for the importance of institutional frameworks in managing student sports development, while Yarlikova (2015) points out the formative impact of physical culture in the general educational process. Together, these studies confirm that physical education and national games are essential for cultivating sustainable health culture and strengthening socio-ethical values among schoolchildren.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The primary objective of the present study is to provide a theoretical rationale and analysis of the current state of physical education and sports. This will be followed by the development of methods for promoting a healthy lifestyle among primary school children. In addition, the study will identify the key principles and stages of their practical implementation in children's lives, with the aim of establishing a culture of health.

There is a broad consensus that the promotion of a healthy lifestyle among primary school children is of paramount importance for the assurance of their physical and psychosocial well-being, as well as the sustainable development of society and the state as a whole. Nevertheless, in recent years there has been a steady trend towards a deterioration in the health indicators of children and adolescents due to a combination of factors. These include a decline in living standards in a number of regions, environmental degradation, an unbalanced diet, and failure to comply with health regulations.

In the context of addressing the issues of promoting a healthy lifestyle among primary school students, the following research objectives were identified:

- The present study will analyse the cognitive, physical, and motivational abilities of primary school students.
- The development and testing of a model for the promotion of a culture of health among children is the objective of this study.
- The following teaching methods are to be introduced: those based on the use of elements of national sports and traditional games.

As part of the study, a survey was conducted among children who practise traditional (folk) sports and games. The analysis of the data took into account the correlation between the somatic status and worldview attitudes of the respondents. Physical exercises and play activities grounded in motor activity represent pivotal methodological approaches within the domains of ethnopedagogy and the physical education system. The systematic integration of these elements within the educational process is instrumental in fostering the harmonious development of students' personalities.

The data obtained indicate the need to revitalise national sports and games that have historically been integrated into the daily practices of the population in both rural and urban areas. At present, these practices are recognised as cultural heritage and are accorded priority.

The revitalisation of these practices necessitates the urgent reconstruction of existing sports facilities and racecourses, as well as the consideration of the construction of new facilities in recreational areas and places of mass gathering, in accordance with the provisions of the Concept for the Development of National Sports and Folk Games.

It has been demonstrated that high-level athletes cultivate personal competencies that determine success in both sports and other areas of activity. The objective of educational influence is to inculcate in children a lasting motivation to engage in sports activities, with an emphasis on national sports and an active lifestyle. The objective of this process is to cultivate fundamental personal attributes encompassing somatic well-being, self-efficacy, a propensity towards personal growth, psychological well-being, resilience, self-regulation, and socially adaptive behaviour. Empirical research has been conducted which demonstrates that a purposeful personality has a positive social impact by demonstrating value-based and meaningful orientations.

It is evident that national sports and folk games play a pivotal role in the harmonious development of the younger generation, ensuring the transmission of ethnocultural experience, historical heritage, and traditional practices. The contemporary physical education system necessitates the incorporation of millennia-old empirical knowledge, meticulously selected through a process of historical and cultural selection, pertinent to the educational potential of folk games and national sports.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the context of the updating of national sports and folk games, the regulatory framework and software for the activities of sports-oriented supplementary education institutions (DUSSE) have been modified, in particular for martial arts and national equestrian disciplines. A significant limiting factor in the development of these practices is the shortage of specialised equipment produced domestically, as well as the inadequacy of the resource base of specialised sports schools to meet the needs of students in the field of national sports. Concurrently, there are outstanding issues with regard to methodological support (scientific and methodological materials) and the development of regulatory, medical, biological, and information-analytical infrastructure. A

review of historical and sporting research reveals that a considerable proportion of formerly prevalent national sporting activities have been consigned to oblivion and are currently undergoing a process of revitalisation.

It is recommended that a network of team-oriented sports clubs be established for primary and secondary school students, with a particular focus on popular team sports. The minimum requirement is to establish at least one such club in each region, with sections dedicated to football, hockey, other sports disciplines, and traditional forms of physical activity (national sports).

Physical education constitutes the foundational element for somatic well-being, the cultivation of human potential, the development of volitional qualities (notably, determination), and the cognitive ability to concentrate when surmounting difficulties. In the case of younger schoolchildren, it is recommended that educational and upbringing processes be implemented in unison, on account of the following physiological and psychosocial effects:

- The induction of morphofunctional adaptations of the musculoskeletal system has been observed, including sarcoplasmic hypertrophy and increased strength indicators.
- The body exhibits an augmented resistance to deleterious exogenous factors.
- The primary objective is the optimisation of anthropometric parameters, the development of neuromotor coordination, and the enhancement of speed of movement and social competence.
- The harmonisation of the cognitive, affective, and conative components of activity is of paramount importance.

The impact of prolonged periods of physical inactivity on the developing human body has been demonstrated to result in a number of adverse consequences. These include degenerative changes in the peripheral nervous system, progressive circulatory disorders, cardiovascular diseases, and increased psychomotor excitability. Individuals exhibiting diminished cardiovascular function are typified by elevated levels of fatigue, a predisposition to dyspnoea, and emotional lability. The phenomenon of inertia (abulia) can be defined as a maladaptive factor that determines negative consequences both at the individual level and in a social-group context.

The cultivation of stable personality traits, encompassing stress resistance (i.e., “combat” qualities), tolerance, kindness, and courage, constitutes a paramount objective of primary school education. It is evident that ethnic and traditional gaming practices have the potential to serve as an effective medium for the cultivation of these qualities. It has been demonstrated that children who have developed empathy and emotional responsiveness (“open heart”) have the capacity to consciously construct adaptive strategies for overcoming adverse circumstances and achieving psychological well-being, while remaining committed to the principles of sincerity and virtue. In this process, methods of psychological self-regulation and personal self-improvement play an important role.

The present generation of primary school students, in conjunction with their engagement in conventional forms of play, exhibits a set of favourable ethnocultural characteristics. The combination of these factors contributes to the satisfaction of current socio-pedagogical demands and ensures the formation of a personality model in younger schoolchildren that is relevant to the requirements of modern society.

Axiological education of primary school students is identified as a pivotal component of the contemporary educational framework, with the objective of fortifying the social foundations of the students. The objective of establishing universal values and fostering deliberate engagement with the external environment in early schoolchildren is realised through their assimilation of conventional models of cultural and spiritual heritage, in conjunction with national traditions. The relevant curricula place a strong emphasis on moral imperatives such as decency, hospitality, and kindness. The primary school generation is introduced to ethnocultural heritage through exposure to national literature and traditional practices. The pedagogical value of play as an effective tool for the education and promotion of a healthy lifestyle is widely acknowledged. The integration of play methods into the educational process has been demonstrated to serve as a means of developing students' cognitive functions. Furthermore, it has been shown to contribute to the internalisation of the spiritual heritage of the ethnic group and its subsequent transmission to new generations.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Pedagogical concepts and established practices of ethnopedagogy in primary education embody world-view attitudes, goal setting, as well as normative prescriptions for individuals, families, and the socialisation process of the younger generation. These practices actualise the continuity of historical experience. It is evident

that national gaming practices constitute an integral element of the conventional pedagogical paradigm. Historically established folk games are determined by a number of factors, including way of life, labour activities, ethnocultural customs, heroic ideals, and an orientation towards moral virtues (honesty, fortitude, patience, etc.). The axiological dominant of this phenomenon can be considered to represent the quintessence of folk wisdom.

References:

1. Doroshkevich M. P., Nashkevich M. A., Murav'eva D. M. i dr. *Osnovy valeologii i shkol'noy gigieny: Ucheb. posobie dlya vuzov.* – M.: Fizkul'tura i sport, 2003. – 238 p.
2. Kengesbayevich, R. M. (2024). Readiness of social pedagogues to work with children with disabilities. *American Journal of Education and Learning*, 2(3), 318–323.
3. Kengesbayevich, R. M. (2025, January). Didactics of physical culture and sport. In *International Conference on Adaptive Learning Technologies* (Vol. 13, pp. 20–21).
4. Kengesbayevich, R. M. (2025, January). Psychological defences in children. In *International Conference on Adaptive Learning Technologies* (Vol. 13, pp. 22–23).
5. Kochashkin V. M. *Metodika fizicheskogo vospitaniya.* – M., 1972. – 315 p.
6. Lubisheva L. I. *Sportizatsiya v obshebrazovatel'noy shkole / Pod obshh. red. L. I. Lubishevoy.* – M.: NIS "Teoriya i praktika fizicheskoy kul'tury", 2009. – 168 p.
7. Luk'yanenko V. P. *Fizicheskaya kul'tura: osnovy znaniy: Uchebnoe posobie.* – Stavropol': Izd-vo SGU, 2001. – 224 p.
8. Peshkova N. V., Peshkov A. A. *Proektirovanie sistemy upravleniya razvitiem studencheskogo sporta v sovremennom vuze. Teoriya i praktika fizicheskoy kul'tury*, (5), 83–85, 2012.
9. Yarlikova O. V. *Formirovanie fizicheskoy kul'tury v obrazovatel'nom prosesse. Professional'naya orientatsiya*, (2), 32–35, 2015.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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